

Tensile and Compressive Properties of C/GFRP-FW Pipes

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ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with the mechanical properties of carbon/glass hybrid FRP-FW pipes. The objective is to establish an engineering design criterion for the effective use of light weight FRP-FW pipes as the structural members. (1) An analytical method which predicts the elastic moduli of FRP laminates has been developed, taking into account the anisotropic elasticity of carbon fiber and the elastic interaction among the fibers. (2) The effects of the winding angle and the addition of hoop winding on tensile and compressive properties of FRP-FW pipes were investigated experimentally. (3) The mechanical properties of GFRP-FW and CFRP-FW pipes were compared. (4) The development of C/GFRP-FW pipes utilizing the both advantages of GFRP and CFRP was attempted. (5) The fracture mechanism of FRP-FW pipes was investigated by applying the extended Huber-Mises criterion for orthotropic materials.

INTRODUCTION

Authors (1,2) have investigated mechanical properties of FRP-FW pipes in order to develop a light weight wheelchair whose frame is made of FRP-FW pipes. In this paper, the elastic moduli and breaking strengths of FRP-FW pipes are investigated fundamentally by means of theoretical analysis and experiments. Effective elastic moduli of unidirectional fiber composites are formulated by applying Eshelby's theory (3), and a laminate theory is developed to predict the elastic moduli of FW pipes. The breaking strengths of FW pipes are examined by applying the extended Huber-Mises criterion (4). Flow chart of the numerical calculation is shown and the results are compared with experimental data. Based on these results, the carbon/glass hybrid FRP-FW pipe which has both of the

advantages of CFRP and GFRP is manufactured and tested.

THEORETICAL (3, 5)

Fundamental Relations

Strain e_{ij} is defined by :

$$e_{ij} = (u_{i,j} + u_{j,i})/2 \quad (1)$$

where u_i is the x_i component of displacement vector. It should be noted that the shear strain e_{12} is 1/2 of the engineering shear strain γ_{12} .

Hooke's Law. Stress and strain relation of matrix(isotropic) is expressed as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} e_{11} &= \frac{1}{E} \sigma_{11} - \frac{\nu}{E} \sigma_{22} - \frac{\nu}{E} \sigma_{33} & e_{23} &= \frac{1}{2\mu} \sigma_{23} \\ e_{22} &= -\frac{\nu}{E} \sigma_{11} + \frac{1}{E} \sigma_{22} - \frac{\nu}{E} \sigma_{33} & e_{31} &= \frac{1}{2\mu} \sigma_{31} \\ e_{33} &= -\frac{\nu}{E} \sigma_{11} - \frac{\nu}{E} \sigma_{22} + \frac{1}{E} \sigma_{33} & e_{12} &= \frac{1}{2\mu} \sigma_{12} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where E, ν is the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the matrix, respectively, and μ is modulus of rigidity (shear modulus).

$$\mu = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)} \quad (3)$$

Fiber (transversely isotropic) has the following stress-strain relation. The fiber axis is taken along the x_3 -axis.

$$\begin{aligned} e_{11} &= \frac{1}{E_1} \sigma_{11} - \frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} \sigma_{22} - \frac{\nu_{13}}{E_3} \sigma_{33} & e_{23} &= \frac{1}{2\mu_{23}} \sigma_{23} \\ e_{22} &= -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} \sigma_{11} + \frac{1}{E_1} \sigma_{22} - \frac{\nu_{13}}{E_3} \sigma_{33} & e_{31} &= \frac{1}{2\mu_{23}} \sigma_{31} \\ e_{33} &= -\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_1} \sigma_{11} - \frac{\nu_{31}}{E_1} \sigma_{22} + \frac{1}{E_3} \sigma_{33} & e_{12} &= \frac{1}{2\mu_{12}} \sigma_{12} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_1} = \frac{\nu_{13}}{E_3}$, $\mu_{12} = \frac{E_1}{2(1+\nu_{12})}$ (5)

C_{ijkl} . Hooke's law can be also expressed by $\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl} e_{kl}$. Elastic moduli of the matrix, C_{ijkl} , and the fiber, C_{ijkl}^* , are :

$$C_{ijkl} = \lambda \delta_{ij} \delta_{kl} + \mu \delta_{ik} \delta_{jl} + \mu \delta_{il} \delta_{jk} \quad , \quad \lambda = \frac{\nu E}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} \quad (6)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} C_{1111}^* &= C_{2222}^* = \frac{E_1(-\nu_{13}^2 E_1 + E_3)}{(1+\nu_{12})Q} & , & \quad C_{2323}^* = C_{3131}^* = \mu_{23} \\ C_{1122}^* &= \frac{E_1(\nu_{13}^2 E_1 + \nu_{12} E_3)}{(1+\nu_{12})Q} & , & \quad C_{1212}^* = \mu_{12} \\ C_{1133}^* &= C_{2233}^* = \nu_{13} E_1 E_3 / Q & , & \quad C_{3333}^* = (1-\nu_{12}) E_3^2 / Q \\ & & & \quad Q = -2\nu_{13}^2 E_1 + (1-\nu_{12}) E_3 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

Unidirectional Fiber Composite

Effective elastic moduli C_{ijkl}^1 and compliance S_{ijkl}^1 of the unidirectional fiber composite can be calculated as follows. The shape of fibers is assumed to be spheroidal with infinite aspect ratio:

$$\frac{x_1^2}{a^2} + \frac{x_2^2}{a^2} + \frac{x_3^2}{c^2} = 1 \quad \left(\frac{c}{a} = \infty \right) \tag{8}$$

Flow Chart.

Initial Identification	
Input Data $E, \nu, E_1, E_3, \nu_{12}, \nu_{13}, \mu_{23}$	(6), (7) $\rightarrow C_{ijkl}, C_{ijkl}^*$
Volume fraction : v_1 (matrix), $v_2 = 1 - v_1$ (fibers)	
Eshelby's tensor	
$T_{1111} = T_{2222} = \frac{5-4\nu}{8(1-\nu)}$	$T_{3311} = T_{3322} = T_{3333} = 0$
$T_{1122} = T_{2211} = \frac{4\nu-1}{8(1-\nu)}$	$T_{2323} = T_{3131} = \frac{1}{4}$
$T_{1133} = T_{2233} = \frac{\nu}{2(1-\nu)}$	$T_{1212} = \frac{3-4\nu}{8(1-\nu)}$

Calculation of S_{ijkl}^1	
<p>(1) $\sigma_{33}^A = 1, \sigma_{ij}^A = 0$ otherwise. \rightarrow</p> <p>$S_{3333}^1 = \frac{1}{E} + v_2 e_{33}^*$</p> <p>(2) $\sigma_{11}^A = \sigma_{22}^A = 1, \sigma_{ij}^A = 0$ otherwise. \rightarrow</p> <p>$S_{1111}^1 + S_{1122}^1 = \frac{1-\nu}{E} + v_2 e_{11}^* \text{ --- (I)}$</p> <p>(3) $\sigma_{12}^A = 1, \sigma_{ij}^A = 0$ otherwise. \rightarrow</p> <p>$2S_{1212}^1 = S_{1111}^1 - S_{1122}^1 = \frac{1}{2\mu} + v_2 e_{12}^* \text{ --- (II)}$</p> <p>$S_{1111}^1 = \frac{(I) + (II)}{2}, \quad S_{1122}^1 = \frac{(I) - (II)}{2}$</p> <p>(4) $\sigma_{11}^A = \sigma_{22}^A = \sigma_{33}^A = 1, \sigma_{ij}^A = 0$ otherwise. \rightarrow</p> <p>$S_{1133}^1 = \frac{1}{4} \left[\frac{3(1-2\nu)}{E} + v_2 (e_{11}^* + e_{22}^* + e_{33}^*) - 2S_{1111}^1 - 2S_{1122}^1 - S_{3333}^1 \right]$</p> <p>(5) $\sigma_{23}^A = 1, \sigma_{ij}^A = 0$ otherwise. \rightarrow</p> <p>$S_{2323}^1 = \frac{1}{4\mu} + \frac{1}{2} v_2 e_{23}^*$</p>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 10px;"> <p>$\sigma_{ij}^A \xrightarrow{(2)} e_{ij}^A$</p> <p>$\downarrow$</p> <p>$C_{pqmn} [e_{mn}^A + v_1 (T_{mnkl} e_{kl}^* - e_{mn}^*)]$</p> <p>$= C_{pqmn}^* [e_{mn}^A + v_1 T_{mnkl} e_{kl}^* + v_2 e_{mn}^*]$</p> <p>$\downarrow$</p> <p>$e_{ij}^*$</p> </div> <p>$\uparrow$ (to (1))</p> <p>\uparrow (to (2))</p> <p>\uparrow (to (3))</p> <p>\uparrow (to (4))</p> <p>\uparrow (to (5))</p>
$S_{ijkl}^1 \rightarrow C_{ijkl}^1$ (inverse matrix)	

Examples. Input Data : Matrix ; $E = 370 \text{ (kg/mm}^2\text{)}$ $\nu = 0.38$

Glass fiber ; $E_1 = E_3 = 7400$ $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.22$ $\mu_{23} = 3032.8$

Carbon fiber ; $E_1 = 1500$ $E_3 = 23000$ $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.3$ $\mu_{23} = 4000$ (6, 7, 8)

Volume fraction of fibers ; $\nu_2 = 0.5$.

Table 1. Effective moduli of unidirectional fiber composite

	GFRP	CFRP		GFRP	CFRP
S_{1111}^1	10.11×10^{-4}	13.61×10^{-4}	C_{1111}^1	1426	996.1
S_{1122}^1	-5.111	-6.752	C_{1122}^1	769.0	505.0
S_{1133}^1	-0.752	-0.2893	C_{1133}^1	641.8	507.4
S_{3333}^1	2.572	0.8557	C_{3333}^1	4263	12030
S_{2323}^1	6.938	6.766	C_{2323}^1	360.3	369.5

Laminated Composite

We consider a laminate composed of N layers of unidirectional fiber composites. The coordinates $\overset{\circ}{x}_i (i=1,2,3)$ are fixed in the specimen, and the coordinate $x_i (i=1,2,3)$ are taken parallel to the principal axes of each layer. $\theta_i (i=1-N)$ is the inclination angle between $\overset{\circ}{x}_3$ -axis and the fiber axis (x_3) of the i-th layer. It is assumed that the strain components of each layer are all identical with those of the laminate in $\overset{\circ}{x}_1$ - $\overset{\circ}{x}_3$ plane. And the stress components in the thickness direction ($\overset{\circ}{x}_2 = x_2$) are assumed to vanish.

$$\overset{\circ}{\sigma}_{22} = \overset{\circ}{\sigma}_{23} = \overset{\circ}{\sigma}_{12} = 0 \tag{9}$$

The effective elastic modulus C_{ijkl}^{**} , and the Young's modulus E_3^{**} and Poisson's ratio ν_{13}^{**} of the laminate can be calculated as follows.

Fig.1. Coordinates $\overset{\circ}{x}_i$ and x_i .

Prediction of Tensile Strength of the Laminate

In a plane stress field, the extended Huber-Mises criterion proposed by Hill (4) is expressed by :

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_L}{X}\right)^2 - \frac{\sigma_L \sigma_T}{XX} + \left(\frac{\sigma_T}{Y}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{LT}}{S}\right)^2 = 1 \tag{10}$$

Breaking stress $\sigma_B(i)$ for the i -th layer ($i=1-N$) can be calculated as follows :

* It is assumed that each layer has the same strain $e_{33}^0, e_{11}^0, e_{22}^0$ is calculated by the plane stress assumption.

First failure will occur in the layer which has the least value of σ_B . Once any one of the layers has failed, the deterioration of the failed layer should be taken into account in order to calculate the second layer's failure and so forth. In our calculation, the elastic deterioration is accounted by changing the thickness ratio t_i of the failed layer to t_i^* :

$$\beta = \frac{t_i^*}{t_i}, \quad 0 \leq \beta < 1 \quad (11)$$

EXPERIMENTAL

Specimens

Fibers used for the FRP-FW pipes are : 1) Glass fiber RS-74PE-535 (Nittobo Co.) with specific gravity of 2.54. 2) Carbon fiber TORAYCA T300 (Toray Co.) with specific gravity of 1.74. One hundred parts by weight (pbw) of epoxy resin EPIKOTE 828 (Shell Chemical Co.) was mixed with 80 pbw of curing agent HHPA and one pbw of promoting catalyzer K61B. The fibers were penetrated with the epoxy resin compound and were formed into FRP pipes by the filament winding method. The FRP-FW pipes were cured at 130°C for 3 hours. The inside diameter and thickness of the FW pipes were about 19mm and 1.5mm, respectively. Fiber content in each layer of FW pipes was measured by burning test.

(±θ)specimen. FW pipes of helical winding (±θ) without the hoop winding.

$\theta = 20^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, \text{ and } 60^\circ.$

($\pm\theta + 90^\circ$) specimen. Both of the inner and outer layers are helical windings ($\pm\theta$) and the middle layer is a hoop winding (90°). Thickness ratio of the hoop layer is about 0.15. $\theta = 20^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ$.

C/G hybrid specimen. (G45 G90 C20), (C20 G90 G45), (G20 G90 C45), and (C45 G90 G20) ; e.g., (G45 G90 C20) = Inner layer ($\pm 45^\circ$ of GFRP) + Middle layer (90° of CFRP) + Outer layer ($\pm 20^\circ$ of CFRP).

Measurements

The length of FRP-FW pipes was 300mm. Tensile and compressive tests were carried out using an Instron 1332 testing machine. The gauge length of the specimens was 200mm and the rates of extension and compression were both 2mm/min. The strain of the specimen was measured by the strain gauge KFR-5-C1-65 (Kyowa Co.). In both tests, steel rods of 19mm diameter and 70mm length were inserted in both ends of the FW pipes to protect against the chuck failure.

RESULTS

Young's modulus vs. winding angle θ .

Fig.2. GFRP-FW ($\pm\theta$)

Fig.3. CFRP-FW ($\pm\theta$)

Fig.4. GFRP-FW ($\pm\theta + 90^\circ$)

Theoretical ($\nu_2=0.5$) : —————

Experimental : ○

Theoretical values agree satisfactorily with the experimental results.

Fig.5. Tensile strength of GFRP-FW ($\pm\theta$).

Fig.6. Tensile strength of CFRP-FW ($\pm\theta$).

{ Theoretical ($\nu_2 = 0.5$) ; Extended Huber-Mises : _____
 { Maximum stress criterion : - - - - -
 Experimental : O

	(kg/mm ²)		
	X	Y	S
GFRP	128	5.2	9.3
CFRP	140	7	12

Fig.7. Tensile strength of GFRP ($\pm\theta + 90^\circ$).

$\nu_2 = 0.5, \beta = 0.8$

Fig.8. Compressive stress-strain relation of C/GFRP-FW pipes. (Experimental results)

Fig.9. Tensile stress-strain relations of C/G hybrid FRP-FW pipes.

B1 : G45 G90 C20
 B2 : C20 G90 G45
 B3 : G20 G90 C45
 B4 : C45 G90 G20

$\beta = 0.8$ for G90
 $\beta = 0$ otherwise

Theoretical : ———
 Experimental : - - - - -

Experimental S-S curves show larger elongation than theoretical estimates,

especially in C45/G20 specimens.
 I : failure of G 90.
 II : failure of C 45.

REFERENCES

- 1 Ban, K., Otsuka, H. and Takahashi, K., "Development of Light Wheelchair with Carbon/Glass Hybrid FRP-FW Pipes," Trans.JSCM, Vol.6, No.1, 1980, pp.9-13
- 2 Ban K., Otsuka, H. and Takahashi, K., "The Effect of Hoop Winding on Mechanical Properties of GFRP-FW Pipes (in Japanese)," J.Society of Fiber Science and Technology, Japan (Sen-i Gakkaishi), Vol.37, No.10, 1981, pp.420-425
- 3 Eshelby, J.D., "The Determination of the Elastic Field of an Ellipsoidal Inclusion, and Related Problems," Proc.Roy.Soc.London, Ser.A, Vol.241, 1957, pp.376-396
- 4 Hill, R., "A Theory of the Yielding and Plastic Flow of Anisotropic Metals," Proc.Roy.Soc.London, Ser.A, Vol.193, 1948, pp.281-297
- 5 Takahashi, K., "Stress Analysis of Particle-Filled Composites, Application of Eshelby's Theory (in Japanese)," J.Japan Society for Composite Materials, Vol.8, No.2, 1982, pp.46-52
- 6 Whitney, J.M., "Elastic Moduli of Unidirectional Composites with Anisotropic Filaments," J.Composite Materials, Vol.1, 1967, pp.188-193
- 7 Murayama, K. and Tanaka, T., "Thermal Expansion of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Composites (in Japanese)," J.Society of Materials Science JAPAN (Zairyo), Vol.25, 1976, pp.417-421
- 8 Ishikawa, T., Koyama, K. and Kobayashi, S., "Elastic Moduli of Carbon-Epoxy Composites and Carbon Fibers," J.Composite Materials, Vol.11, 1977, pp.332-344